

Investigating the Relationship between Social Capital and Organizational Leadership (Case Study: Calcimin Company in Zanjan Province)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Ali Almasi ⁽²⁾Kamran Yeganegi ⁽³⁾Abolfazl Moghaddam ⁽¹⁾Department of Executive Management, Islamic Azad University-zanjan Branch, zanjan, Iran ⁽²⁾Department of Industrial Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan Branch, Zanjan, Iran. ⁽³⁾Department of Executive Management, Islamic Azad University-zanjan Branch, zanjan, Iran

Abstract:

For development in the present, we need more social capital than economic, physical and human capital, because, without this capital, the optimal use of other capital is not possible. In the past, social capital was not explicitly taken into consideration, but at present, changing environmental acceleration, information technology, the growing need for information and education, the growing need for innovation and creativity, and the need for continuous improvement of the organization. Which leaders of organizations consider social capital as an invaluable organizational resource. On the other hand, organizational initiatives are one of the important tools for measuring the performance of organizations. Hence, the main purpose of this study is to explain the relationship between social capital and organizational leadership in the company of calcimin. The research method is a descriptive survey of the applied type, and the statistical population of this research is 435 people including employees and managers of the company calcimin. According to the Cochran sampling formula, 160 of them were selected as the sample. In this research, the main hypothesis and three sub-hypotheses As a result of the hypothesis test, all the assumptions were confirmed, and the relationship between social capital and its three dimensions as independent variables was confirmed by the organizational lead as a dependent variable. Following the research findings, functional and operational proposals were presented separately from the hypotheses.

Keywords: Social Capital, Organizational Leadership, and calcimin Company

1. Introduction

In today's fast-paced world, organizations are working to achieve organizational and economic goals and use different patterns and methods to survive and gain a new competitive advantage in order to avoid falling and downturns and the dangers of rapid environmental change.

In traditional views of development management, economic, physical, and human capital played the most important role; for development in the present, we need more social capital than economic, physical and human capital, since without this capital the optimal use of other capital Not possible. In the past, social capital was not explicitly taken into consideration, but at present, changing environmental acceleration, information technology, the growing need for information and education, the growing need for innovation and creativity, and the need for continuous improvement of the organization. Which leaders of organizations consider social capital as an invaluable organizational resource (Rahmanpour, 2003, 80).

These factors enable organizations to improve their ability and capacity to create and deliver value to the organization's stakeholders, and in particular to citizens, and to define more effective models of excellence and to implement a more valuable process of innovation that leads to their success It turns out. Government agencies and institutions can discover new strategic resources to achieve organizational excellence and excellent performance outcomes (Park, 2009).

The resource-based approach emphasizes that in the age of turbulence and rapid changes in technology and the needs of customers and industries, there is a sustainable competitive advantage and excellence of the requirements of organizations, and this is a benefit and excellence stemming from the social capital of the organization. (Josh Maria, 2004)

2. Social capital

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Table 1 lists some of the definitions of social capital:

Social capital descriptions	Pundits
The ability of individuals for sustainable benefits through membership in social networks or other social structures	Ports
A unique personal communication network and privileged institutional affiliation	Belliveau, OReilly, Wade
A context of cooperative relationships among citizens who help each other to resolve problems	Barham,Ran
The ability of individuals to collaborate and support for public purposes in groups and organizations	Fukuyama
Social capital is defined by its function. Social capital is not a unitary thing, but a variety of things, all of which have two common features: first, they include an aspect of a social fabric; and two, certain actions of individuals within the structure, whether they are natural persons or legal entities And facilitate the achievement of certain goals that will be unattainable in the absence of it	Coleman
Norms and networks that allow people to participate in collective actions for mutual benefit and can be measured by methods such as measuring the level of social trust and levels of membership in formal or informal civil society associations	Tajbakhsh, saghafi, and kohestani Nezhad
Social capital is at the very beginning a process of processes that lead to outsourcing, which is the result of social action. Thus, the social crisis is a social action class and includes those hands that either endure themselves or affect those who are durable	Collier

The scholars have raised the eight major elements of social capital as follows:

- Participation in the local community
- Activism in a social position
- Feeling trust and security
- Neighborhood links
- Friendship and family ties
- Capacity to accept differences
- Costing and living
- Work Links

As can be seen, each of the above definitions refers to an aspect of social capital, but in all of these definitions, trust has been named as the main component of social capital. In these definitions, psychological indicators (trust and norms) and behavioral (networks) are combined.

Trusting the meaning of belief is based on the possibility that others do private work or refrain from doing so.

The concept of trust may be based on the prediction of a partner's behavior in terms of his obligations and obligations and the possibility of anticipating his behavior in negotiations and interactions while he may face opportunistic behavior.

In research texts, they differentiate trust into different types of researchers, and researchers have mentioned at least three different types of trust:

- Trust of relatives and relatives: that expresses the trust of people in the community to family members, relatives, and friends;
- Social trust among individuals: which expresses the trust of individuals towards each other and the community
- Institutional trust: It perceives people's feelings towards different institutions or professions, or even different government sectors.

Indeed, among the components of social capital, which is trust, networks, coherence, and participation, trust is the most important component or indicator.

3. Organizational Leader

Propaganda in the word means getting up and getting better. Organizational Leadership means an organizational commitment to sustained and sustained growth and development of the organization in order to achieve customer satisfaction and continually increase profitability in a widespread and supportive national environment. Organizational orientation is subject to specific conditions, culture, internal and external business environment, the manpower of the organization, the strengths and weaknesses, the pitfalls and threats that the organization embraces, in a word, the path to excellence of organizational excellence, identification, recognition Is the development and expansion of success in an organization (Beikzad, 2009).

Different people from different perspectives have different meanings. So that each group of employees, managers, and clients of an organization interpret their own particularities from the transcendental organization. Employees recognize the organization's excellence in the proper legal system and amenities. Excellency managers have long-term goals and appropriate solutions to achieve them. Customers also find the right products and services at the right time to be the characteristics of a supranational organization and expect the organization to value them and provide them with their needs. On the other hand, all of the listed groups live in a community. Exceptional and prominent organizations are organizations that bring all the results they have gained and the confidence they have in preserving the results in the endeavor to satisfy all stakeholders.

Propaganda requires leadership commitment and acceptance of fundamental concepts, a set of general principles that govern these behaviors, activities, and behaviors based on these rules. When the organization repeats these general rules, the field of assessment of sustainable excellence is created.

4. Research model

Figure 1 shows an overview of the model that shows the dynamics of the model. Learning, creativity and innovation help improve enablers, and improving empowerment will improve results

Each of the nine criteria of the Organizational Excellence Award Model consists of several components that specify the various dimensions of the benchmark.

- Benchmark 1: Leadership
- Benchmark 2: Strategy
- Benchmark 3: Staff

- Benchmark 4: Partnerships and Resources
- Benchmark 5: Processes, Products and Services
- Benchmark 6: Customer Results
- Benchmark 7: Employee Results
- Benchmark 8: Community Results
- Benchmark 9: Key Results

5. The results of the research

Table 2 shows the results of the Pearson correlation test between the structural dimensions of social capital and organizational change using SPSS software.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Test between Structural Dimension of Social Capital and Organizational Leadership

Independent variable (social capital structural indicators)	Dependent Variable	Organizational excellence (staff)	Organizational Excellence (Managers)
	Pearson Correlation test		
Network links	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0/400**	0/289
	Significance level (P)	0/001	0/121
	Number(N)	130	30
Network status	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0/250**	0/310
	Significance level (P)	0/004	0/096
	Number(N)	130	30
Good organization	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0/391**	0/302
	Significance level (P)	0/001	0/105
	Number(N)	130	30

According to the results of the correlation matrix table (Table 4-15), it can be said that among the employees of the statistical sample with the confidence of 0.99 and 0.01 error level between the net

Table 3: Pearson correlation test between the cognitive dimension of social capital and organizational innovation Work link index of social capital and organizational excellence,

Independent variable (Cognitive dimension of social capital)	Dependent Variable	Organizational Leadership (Employees)	Organizational Leadership (Managers)
	Pearson Correlation test		
Common languages and codes	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0/444**	0/334
	Significance level (P)	0/001	071/0
	Number (N)	130	30

There is. On the other hand, the value of this relationship ($P < 0/01$), which equals 0.4, is directly (positive) and is moderate. Also, the results of Table 4-15 show that there is a meaningful relationship between the status of the network indicator and the social capital and organizational incentives. ($P < 0/01$) The value of this relationship is 0.25 and indicates the weakness of the relationship. In addition, there is a

meaningful relationship between the appropriate organization index and the social capital and organizational incentives ($P < 0/01$). The value of this relationship is 0.391 and indicates the weakness of this relationship. According to the results of Table 2 in the sample managers, there is no statistically significant relationship between any of the structural dimension indicators of the social capital variable (network links, network status, proper organization) and organizational change variable. ($P > 0/05$).

Table 3 shows the results of the Pearson correlation test between the cognitive dimension of social capital and organizational change through SPSS software.

According to the results obtained from the correlation matrix table (Table 3), it can be said that among the employees of the statistical sample with confidence of 0.99 and the level of 0.01 error between the language index and the common codes of the variable of social capital and organizational excellence, ($P < 0.01$). On the other hand, the value of this relationship, which is 0.444, is directly (positive) and is moderate. According to the results of this table, in the group of sample managers, there is not a meaningful relationship between the language index and the common codes, i.e., the cognitive dimension of social capital, and organizational orientation ($P > 0.05$).

Table 4 shows the results of the Pearson correlation test between the relationship between social capital and organizational capital using SPSS software.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Test between Relative Dimensional Dimensions of Social Capital and Organizational Leadership

Independent variable (dimensional indices of social capital relations)	Dependent variable	Organizational Leadership	Organizational Leadership
	Pearson Correlation test	Leadership	Leadership
the trust	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	(Employees)	(Managers)
	Significance level (P)	481**/0	331/0
	Number (N)	001/0	074/0
The norm	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	130	30
	Significance level (P)	316**/0	351/0
	Number (N)	001/0	057/0
Requirements	Pearson Correlation	130	30
	of Coefficient	397**/0	300/0
	Significance level (P)	001/0	107/0
Identity	(N) Number	130	30
	Pearson Correlation	436**/0	144/0
	of Coefficient	001/0	449/0
obligation Independent variable (dimensional indices of social capital relations)	Significance level (P)	130	30
	(N) Number	560**/0	235/0
	Pearson Correlation	001/0	211/0

According to the results of the correlation matrix table (Table 4-17), it can be said that among the employees, the statistical sample with confidence of 0.99 and the level of error is less than 0.01 between the indicators of trust, norm, requirements, identity, and commitment There is a relationship between social capital and organizational excellence ($P < 0.01$).

On the other hand, the value of these relationships, which is 0.481, 0.316, 0.397, 0.436, 0.560 respectively, indicates the direct (positive) relationship of these indices with the organizational progression variable. Also, considering the values of these relationships, it can be concluded that the relationship between normative indices and requirements with organizational orientation, weak relationship, and the relationship between trust, identity, and commitment indicators with organizational excellence are moderate.

In addition, the results of the same table (Table 17-17) indicate that there is no statistically significant relationship between any of the indicators of relational dimension and organizational orientation in the manager's group.

6. Summaries and Conclusions

Social capital plays a very important role in organizations and societies. In the absence of social capital, other capital loses its effectiveness, and the path to development and organizational excellence becomes rugged and difficult.

Meanwhile, trust, norms, commitment, commitment and network links will lead to high quality of service and satisfaction of the stakeholders of the organization. This research showed that social capital is effective on organizational leadership, and not only employees and managers of this company, but also other organizations can also use appropriate methods such as building trust between members of the organization and organizational units, participating and expanding networks Among the members of the organization, encouraging and forming groups and committees of product promotion and quality service committees, and the committee reiterates the client's appeal to the organization to increase the social capital of employees and ultimately achieve the achievement of organizational excellence.

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